

**FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEMOCRATIC JOURNALISM IN MONGOLIA:
POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE ASPECTS****Zulkaphil M.,***Prof., Ph.D., Dr.Sc. in History,**Department of Journalism and Mass Communication,**National University of Mongolia***Purevgochoo G.***Master's student,**Department of Journalism and Mass Communication,**National University of Mongolia***Abstract**

It has been more than 30 years since the foundation of free press was laid in Mongolia. During this period, along with the increase in the number of mass media outlets, there have been significant changes in the content of media articles and programs, and the coverage and immediacy of news have improved. Although there are such positive trends in regard to the development and maturation of democratic journalism, there are a number of challenges that need to be addressed. Therefore, in this article, the author discusses the characteristics, trends, current situation, and positive and negative aspects of the development of free press in Mongolia. Moreover, the author analyzes the factors affecting journalistic ethics and responsibility on the basis of specific case studies, and offers suggestions to address the pressing problems.

Keywords: democratic journalism, journalist's ethics, free press, public information, media control, pluralism, public opinion, information prompt.

One of the greatest successes that Mongolia has achieved during the last 30 years since it stepped into democracy and open society is the fact that a free press was formed and became a reality. Although in the past our country did not experience the development of a free press and lacked specialists to carry out the task of developing a free press, today the whole recognizes that Mongolia is a country with a free press. Moreover, Mongolia stands in the front row among the post-socialist countries according to these indices. Free press – the rostrum of openness and pluralism – is an inseparable component of democracy. Is this impossible to imagine free press without democracy or vice versa. A famous politician once said, "There cannot be a democracy without freedom of press. Since any problem must be open to the public, it is impossible to solve the accumulated conflicts and arguments without freedom of press". This quote emphasizes the importance of the free press in a society. Therefore, the role of free press is often compared with "fourth estate," "fourth power," and "watchdog."

Since pluralism was accepted in Mongolia in 1990 and was confirmed by the new Constitution in 1992, a whole network of free press appeared in a relatively short period of time. Although journalism went through a complicated path and faced a number of obstacles, it is advancing step by step and has found its way to development.

First, it is worth to note some of the positive phenomena that can be seen in the activities of our journalism. As the number of media organizations exceeded 1,000 and a large information network was formed, the promptness and accessibility of information have apparently improved. Some vivid examples are the fact that 11 newspapers are published daily (a total of 201 newspapers and magazines), TV channels broadcast their programs nationwide, and total number of 84 ra-

dio stations (34 of them are FM radios) and 146 television stations function in the whole country [8]. Free press is playing an important role in the development of freedom of expression and is allowing Mongolian citizens to enjoy their Constitution-granted rights. This is evident from the increasing number of letters sent to editorial offices, in which people express their opinions, give their comments about current social problems and offer possible solutions. The editorial offices also pay special attention to such letters, as they are the bridge between the public and the government, as well as the source of important publications and programs. They help journalism become the rostrum of openness and pluralism and achieve the role to control. They are one of the clear examples of how people's trust in journalism is increasing.

The roles of media to inform, educate, communicate, supervise, and entertain have become more significant. Our media are concentrating on making information prompt, accessible, open, and pluralist. It is visible from the content of publication and broadcast policy of any media that our journalism is stepping forward to adopt the functions and principles of world free press and is paying attention to the audience's needs and interests. In brief, the theories and methodologies of our journalism have changed and are developing further.

In recent years, the capacity of some newspapers and other forms of media has increased. Our journalists began using structural and composite methods of journalism that are commonly used in the West, such as "inverse pyramid" and "unity of intensive movements." This is surely a progressive step in the skills of our journalists. Also, the quantity of useful and active information is rising. These examples suggest that new trends, which are often seen in the practice of world free press, are penetrating our journalism.

It is worth noting here that several steps were taken in the past to establish a legal environment for free press. In 1987, the Board to Control Media was abolished and broadcasts were no longer censored. In 1992, the *Rules to Run Media* was changed and it became easier to run media. These changes had a very important role in making media more independent. The "Freedom of Press and Information Act" was passed in 1998 and was implemented in January, 1999. Thus, free press became a reality in Mongolia. Although this law has only a few provisions and has not been able to solve many problems concerning the legal regulation of media, it is significant in forbidding censoring public information, establishing organizations, banning sensor information, financing such organizations, forbidding governmental institutions to have any forms of media. In 2000, the UN Committee of Human Rights discussed the Mongolian government's presentation on the "Implementation of Civil and Political Rights Pact" and wrote in their conclusion: "We are very pleased that Mongolia has passed a law about freedom of press" [5, p.83].

All these factors caused media to compete for information and improved the content, style, appearance, and writing methods of newspapers and other publications. The results of our several surveys conducted among the audience prove the statement above. In 2022, under the project "Formation of Free Press and Public Opinion," the Department of Journalism at the National University of Mongolia conducted a survey of 1500 people from both the countryside and the city. According to the results, 54 percent of the participants (810 people) answered that the basis of free press has formed in Mongolia. 27 percent (405 people) answered that free press is developing quite well, and only one percent answered that there is no free press at all. Also, 10.3 percent of the participants believed that our media and journalists have influence in solving the social and political problems, and 83.6 percent thought that they are influential in solving problems in general [7, p.98].

There are not only such positive phenomena and trends in our journalism, but also negative phenomena that might become obstacles to the development of free press. In the beginning of the 1990s, the independence of media became a real fact and a free press was formed. On one hand, it was a destined change which occurred in our society, but on the other hand, many mechanical changes were introduced to regulate the functions of free press. In other words, the second of the four theories of media, the liberalism theory, or the complete freedom of media, penetrated into the practice of our journalism in a very short time. This event was followed by a number of negative consequences.

The number of media, which was below 100, exceeded 1,000 very quickly. Many newspapers, radios and televisions devoted to various topics and tendencies have appeared, and many nonprofessionals have entered the field of journalism. As a result, professional journalism has become the journalism of amateurs. The skills and variety of broadcasts have become poor.

All kinds of controls not only on the content, but also on the content, but also on the composition, grammar, and appearance of broadcasts and publications

have been abolished. Poor comprehension by both journalists and the audience about the nature of freedom of media caused the emergence of "ultimate free press" instead of just free press. Media became a tool to accuse, insult, look for profits, achieve fame, take revenge, overstep in others' private lives, and pursue gossip. Journalists have begun to grossly violate the following principles: "To respect the truth and the rights of the people who want to know the truth is one of the first responsibilities of a journalist" as described in "The Ethical Principles of Journalists" of the International Association of Journalists; and "To make detailed analyses, to correct the mistakes, and to verify the data before publishing an article" as written in the "Ten Commandments of Free Press". All these shortcomings allowed journalists to disobey the professional ethics in each of their steps and to forget their social responsibilities. Furthermore, journalists have lost their reputation among the public and journalism has lost its value. Researchers of journalism in Mongolia say, "The level of journalists' professional ethics has fallen down dramatically; their reputation is not much better than that of criminals who kill and steal, and journalists are selling their only weapon – pen- and their sole property – intelligence". Not only professional researchers of journalism, but also ordinary people admit this.

Our sociological survey, "The Formation of Free Press and Public Opinion," conducted in 2022 among the populace also proves this widely-held belief. 81.3 percent of the participants said that Mongolian journalists violate the ethical norms somehow. 29 percent of all the participants in the survey graded Mongolian journalists as "bad" [7, p.76]. This is a worrisome fact for a small and scarcely populated country like Mongolia.

This abnormal phenomenon which has occurred in our journalism annoyed politicians and the public. Therefore, it has become necessary to take reactive measures, which, in turn, cause unfavorable consequences to the journalist's jobs. These measures were the new provisions added to the Mongolian criminal and Civil Codes. It is now legally required to arrest, fine, or deprive a journalist of the right to work, if they falsely accuse or insult someone without just cause. So far, two female journalists have been penalized under these provisions. Today, many journalists and professional journalistic organizations are making requests to the government to change these provisions but there are still no results.

According to the survey conducted by a non-governmental organization, Globe International, 178 civil cases and nine criminal cases about rehabilitation due to materials spread by the media were settled at court between 2001 and 2006. Although these cases take a relatively small percentage among all the civil and criminal cases settled at court, they make up quite a large percentage if compared to the time elapsed and to the number of all media in our country. In 146 out of the 178 civil cases relating to reputation, the court ruled that the journalists and media involved had damaged the plaintiffs' reputations. Moreover, journalists were connected to five of nine cases about rehabilitation. If we classify the individuals who brought cases to the

court, politicians composed 27 percent, government officials 10 percent, governmental organizations were 4 percent, businessmen 21 percent, artists and sportsmen were 12 percent and others made up the remaining 26 percent. One fact takes our attention is that the media could not prove the trueness of the news and materials they published and broadcasted in 59.6 percent of all the cases settled by the court [2, p.124]. From here, we may come to the following conclusions:

The media pay little attention to the trueness of the materials they are publishing and broadcasting and do not edit them carefully. Such irresponsibility causes grave legal and ethical mistakes.

Journalists do not realize what kind of negative consequences unreal information can bring about and do not think that they to be responsible before the law. In other words, Mongolian journalists lack legal knowledge.

Mongolian journalists often say that there is no complete legal environment for the proper development of media and there is high pressure from the government. However, we-the researchers of journalism- feel the legal environment of media is not very bad. The problem is that journalists do not exercise their freedom and opportunities correctly, do not realize their responsibilities, and do not follow the professional ethical norms. Because of this, they are involved in various problems, are called before court, and are lose their reputations. We need legal acts to protect the journalists' rights, to make political information open and accessible, and conceal sources of information.

Today the biggest obstacle that worries the audience and researchers is the poor skills and ethics of journalists. Most newspapers have only one style, very few genres, several old topics (political arguments, people's private lives, gossips, etc.), and are full of many mechanical, stylistic, and factual mistakes. Before the 1990s, the newspaper *Truth (Unen)* was the prime example of a newspaper written in correct grammars. Today, however, one can easily find at least 10 grammatical mistakes in any Mongolian newspaper. There are even more awkward mistakes like switching names, incorrectly writing the names of the politicians, and guessing some of the facts and data. This is evidence of the complete abolishment of inner control of the editorial offices. It also proves that the self-requirements of journalists are too loose. When media first became independent and many newspapers affected, the entrance of many-nonprofessionals affected the content, style, and proficiency of broadcast and publication. Our media still has not recovered from these shortcomings. Because these new nonprofessionals did not have the necessary basic background knowledge of journalism, they often called a small piece of writing "news," some questions and answers an "interview," and a composition in which opinions are expressed an "ruminations" Even today, most newspapers write mostly these three genres. They do not know other genres.

One the other hand, they wrongly understood the concepts of free press and freedom, so that they began to write anything they wanted, exaggerate the facts, and even fabricating stories. The extremely biased views of

such journalists disturb the balance of information, confuse the populace and gave the wrong idea. As a result, the capacity of information has fallen down and useful, active information has decreased. All these factors have reduced to number of subscribers and the number of readable, high-quality, enlightening newspapers. The famous Mongolian scholar and writer, Tudev Lodon, once wrote: "An important economical index of journalists is determined by how they use the space in newspapers, magazines, and television screens and how they improve the density of radio waves. Pages of newspapers and magazines should be dedicated to dense and refined materials. Writing an essay or an interview with such information that could fit in a small news article or filling in the gaps with redundant words or idle talk is harmful to the journalist himself and to the reader's precious time" [6, p.93].

Nowadays, as the value and significance of information are rising, globalization is taking place, people's ability to receive information is widening, and education is improving, the capacity, quality, and proficiency of information are also getting more and more important. It is clear that the quality and proficiency of Mongolian broadcasts and publications cannot provide for the audience's increasing intellectual needs and requirements. Moreover, our media serves and protects groups of people and political powers. When reading the work of journalists or exchanging opinions with them, one can easily notice that their general education is poor and their ability to enter and feel the authenticity of various issues and problems is deficient. There are very few publications and broadcast programs which pose problems, criticize acutely, analyze deeply, expose causes and effects, and ruminate creatively and pluralistically. Our journalists lack creativity, enthusiasm, research, diligence, and interdisciplinary knowledge. The populace is almost tired of journalists' excessive conclusions, predictions, teachings, and hidden advertisements. Therefore, the following questions arise: What to do now? How to switch from quantity to quality? What are the ways to reduce the above-mentioned negative phenomena? Before answering these questions, I would like to bring up one example:

A hundred years ago, a new form of journalism has formed in the USA, and "yellow press" newspapers, dedicated to the uneducated lower class, appeared in huge numbers. Such newspapers increased by geometric progress. They had too much freedom and it became an ordinary event to violate the social responsibilities and ethical norms. The public, government and researchers of journalism were annoyed by this phenomenon and resisted it in various ways. In response to this phenomenon, the Commission on the Freedom of the Press, led by Robert Hutchins, the president and a professor of Chicago University, was established in 1942. They conducted a comprehensive analysis of the freedom of American press and released their famous paper, "About Responsible and Free Press" (1947). The idea of a responsible freedom of journalism, which is widely used around the world today, was based on this paper. The main idea is that a press must be free but its

freedom must be limited, and it must be responsible to society, moral, and civilized. Owing to this active and creative step, a responsible free press was formed in the USA.

Mongolian journalism reminds one of American journalism one hundred years ago. It is time for us, too, to make a substantial step to shape a moral and responsible journalism. In order to solve this problem successfully, it is necessary to solve the following problems first:

Although the Association of Mongolian Journalists enacted the "Ethical Principles of Mongolian Journalists" in 2005 and started to follow it, they have not achieved any results yet. Several such ethical acts were passed in the past, but each time there were no visible results. The main reason is that there is no mechanism to force those principles into practice. Therefore, we need to establish a Press Council or a Committee of Journalists' ethics, which are widespread in the West. If such an organization were to be established, journalists would be able to solve any arguments connected to media without turning to judicial powers. Moreover, it would allow journalists to be aware of ethical principles and realize their responsibilities. In Mongolia, MONTSAME Agency undertook the beginning of such work and released the *Golden Rules of MONTSAME* and the *Handbook of MONTSAME*. However, this had no effect on other organizations. The power and skills of researchers of journalism and experienced managers and journalists should be used to complete this task.

It is necessary to strengthen the self-control of journalists and the inner control of editorial offices and to make the requirements to new journalists stricter. Carefully checking the mechanical, grammatical, stylistic, factual, and contextual mistakes of news articles will improve the quality of broadcast and publication and will prevent journalists from getting involved in serious problems. Sometimes articles are published without any supervision. Before the 1990s, four to five people used to read and edit a single article. Even if it is impossible to rebuild this system, at least two to three people to review and edit each article.

There should be systemized, well-organized trainings to improve not only professional, but also social, political, economical, and legal knowledge of journalists. Professional organizations of journalists such as the Mongolian Press Institute and the Association of Mongolian Journalists should pay special attention to this matter. Sending the journalists for appointment to foreign countries and organizing exchange of experiences will improve their skills, practice and knowledge. In recent years, the number of colleges and universities that offer journalism programs has reached 14. On the one hand, it is a good thing, but on the other hand, the new graduates do not satisfy modern requirements because of low education, an insufficient number of teachers, and a poor supply of materials. We need to improve the journalistic education, update the academic curriculum, train the teachers better and raise the admissions requirements. We know from our experience that good journalists are born when we accept those who are truly interested in journalism or who

have natural talents. There will not be any good journalists when we accept anyone who wants to enter. Without changing this system, it is ridiculous senseless to talk about moral and responsible journalism.

One of the main factors of the development of journalism is research and critique. It is impossible to improve the quality and efficiency of broadcasts and publications, and the ethics and responsibilities of journalists without prospering theoretical ideas, giving comments to the trends of development, concluding journalists' achievements and shortcomings, and forming the ability to accept criticisms honestly. Although journalism in Mongolia has seen much prosperity and the numbers of professional textbooks, research papers, and researchers of journalism have increased in recent years, we still need to develop the critique of journalism, unite the researchers' powers, conduct much research, and launch projects involving a number of important questions. In particular, our critique of journalism is in a dormant state. That is because our researchers do not have the ability to accept honest criticism and prudent comments, and do not have the conscience to find out and correct their own mistakes. Quite commonly, they lose their reputation by defending themselves, resisting criticism, attacking researchers, and taking revenge.

In order to form and develop free press, a favorable legal environment is necessary like air and water. A favorable legal environment for free press has not yet completely formed in Mongolia. Not only journalists, but also lawyers and researchers of journalism admit this. Mongolian laws are mostly dedicated not to protect free press, but to protect the reputation of individuals and legal entities. Legislators did not consider that freedom of press and the liberty of the public to receive information would be breached in a democratic society. Therefore, it is now important to update some laws, verify journalists' rights to collect information, confirm their rights to conceal and protect the sources of information if necessary, and to ease mechanisms that run media. It is also crucial to pay attention to the financial state of a free press. According to a survey conducted by the non-governmental organization Globe International, 40 percent of the televisions, 31 percent of the radio stations, and the same percent of the newspapers in Mongolia experienced loss in 2004 [2, p.118]. This survey proves that media in Mongolia is in a difficult situation financially. Therefore, free press will prosper if the taxes for media are reduced and imported machines, papers and other materials used in press factories are exempted from taxes.

Thus, during the years of democratic revolution and socio-political and economic reforms, Mongolian journalism played a significant role in destroying the old structures and creating a new, civil, democratic society. Despite the failures and obstacles encountered during the transition period, Mongolian journalism has reached the global standard of free democratic journalism, which is one of the main achievements of our country. In the current conditions of democratization of society in our country, the tasks of Mongolian journalism are becoming more complicated, because the prob-

lems facing the government and the people are becoming more complex. There is a crucial need for a scientifically reasoned analysis of pressing issues of life, for the development of positive recommendations to tackle current problems related to building a new democratic civil society, for the fullest use of the opportunities inherent in all social functions and principles of independent journalism, as well as for the skills of journalists and the genres of publications and media broadcasts.

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